

Photon Emission/Absorption Suggesting that Massive Particles Follow $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$?

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Newtonian mechanics introduces the idea of conservation of energy and momentum, but in a potential field $V(x)$, an interaction occurs in each $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$. Thus, this conservation essentially occurs at a point in space and time. On the other hand, it has been known that a photon interferes with a 2-slit apparatus since the early 1800s. Apparently, photons were originally thought to be waves in a medium like water waves, string waves and sound. Later, Maxwell showed that photon solutions arise from his electromagnetic equations and involve periodic ($\cos(-\omega t+kx)$) electric and magnetic fields. The notion of a physical wave in a medium still persisted, it seems, because it was Einstein (about 1905) who argued that in the photoelectric situation, the photon energy was not spread over space, but acted at a point in an interaction. Thus, it seems that Einstein's ideas lead to the $\cos(-\omega t+kx)$ form (or $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as a complex number) and represents a kind of probability with impulse hits and energy changes occurring in a stochastic manner within the time period and wavelength.

Given that photons may be absorbed and emitted (which was known before 1925), and that presumably energy and momentum is conserved in such interactions, we suggest that given that a photon has a stochastic form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, one must also have such a form for the particle with mass. A particle with mass does not then interact (conserving momentum and energy) in $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$ when interacting with a photon and there is no reason to believe that it would do so when interacting with another massive particle. Newtonian mechanics, however, is experimentally verified, so one may suggest that as long the wavelength \hbar/p and frequency \hbar/E are small with respect to dx and dt values which approximate zero in the macroscopic world, there is no contradiction.

We further argue that if a photon is emitted in a probabilistic way in space such that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ holds, then this probability must ensure conservation of momentum with the atom. We have argued that the atom should be represented by $\exp(ip_{\text{final}}x)$ (spatially) and so one has initially an atom with $\exp(ip_{\text{initial}}x)$ and finally $\exp(ip_{\text{final}}x) \exp(ip_{\text{photon}}x)$. One may formally write the latter as $F(x)$ and expand in terms of $\exp(ipx)$ s as in a mathematical Fourier series because $\exp(ipx)$ is a mathematical representation. Then, a weight linked with p_{initial} is given by: $\int dx \exp(-ip_{\text{initial}}x) \exp(ip_{\text{final}}x) \exp(ip_{\text{photon}}x)$ which yields conservation of momentum.

We further note that in special relativity, if one does not consider the rest frame, then a photon with pc, E and a particle with pc, E transform in the same manner. They do not have the same speed, but interactions are described in terms of p and E and one does not need to know the speed explicitly to describe them. Thus, a massive particle and photon appear on the same footing in the theory of relativity which, we argue, suggests that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ holding for both is consistent with the theory of relativity.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics seems to pertain to particles with rest mass as it uses expressions such as momentum $p=mv$ and kinetic energy $= .5mv^2$. It also introduces the idea of conservation of momentum and energy. A key notion, however, is that given a potential $V(x)$, changes (consistent with conservation of momentum and energy) occur in $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$.

The Case of the Photon

In the early 1800s, the interference of photons with a 2-slit apparatus was studied and it was concluded that light is a physical wave, similar to a string or water wave or sound. In the late 1800s, Maxwell was able to describe a photon mathematically by a periodic electric and magnetic field (perpendicular to each other and the motion) and linked with $\cos(-Et+px)$, but presumably the notion of a wave in a medium persisted because it was Einstein (about 1905) who argued that to understand the photoelectric experiment, one cannot consider a photon as having its energy spread out in space as a wave. When interacting, it would take too long to bring in this energy in a physical wave picture. It seems then that the notion of stochastic momentum hits for a photon appears with Einstein in 1905 because the 2-slit experiment must be explained and there is no physical wave in a medium. We suggest that one may generalize $\cos(-wt+kx)$ to $\exp(-iEt+px)$ to describe the stochastic nature of photon hits and energy changes.

Interaction of a Photon with an Atom

Before 1925 (and deBroglie's wavelength of a massive particle work), it was known that an atom may absorb a photon and then later emit it. In other words, a photon may interact with a massive particle and presumably energy and momentum are conserved. We suggest that one now has an issue. According to Newtonian mechanics, a change in momentum of a massive particle occurs in $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$, but a photon interacts in a stochastic manner and so the incoming photon may give p impulse hits at different x points probabilistically. When being emitted, the photon interaction hit may also be at different x points (linked to action reaction with the atom). Thus, we argue, that in such photon-atom interactions one cannot argue that conservation of momentum simply occurs at a given x point. Instead, if $\exp(ipx)$ describes a photon, $\exp(ip \text{ particle } x)$ should describe the particle as well. This means that this stochastic hits picture must internally conserve momentum. If $\exp(ip \text{ initial})$ is the initial momentum of an excited atom and $\exp(ip \text{ photon } x) \exp(ip \text{ particle final } x)$ are the product (AND) probabilities, then how does one see conservation of momentum without imposing it?

We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ is a math representation and should follow math (i.e. Fourier series rules). If $\exp(ip \text{ photon } x) \exp(ip \text{ particle final } x)$ is called $F(x)$, then one may expand:

$$F(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx) \text{ where } a(p) = \text{constant} \int dx \exp(-ipx) F(x) \quad ((1))$$

Applying this rule to the above situation, one has the weight:

$$\text{Constant Integral } dx \exp(-i p_{\text{initial}} x) \exp(i p_{\text{photon}} x) \exp(i p_{\text{particle}} \text{ final } x) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is 0 if $p_{\text{initial}} \neq p_{\text{photon}} + p_{\text{particle}} \text{ final}$ ((3))

Hence, conservation of momentum naturally appears from the calculation.

Here we work in one dimension. Similar ideas may be applied to $\exp(-iEt)$.

As a result, we suggest that the stochastic properties of a photon, together with its interaction with a massive particle and conservation of momentum and energy lead to the stochastic notion of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ holding for a massive particle as well.

Newtonian Mechanics?

Newtonian mechanics has been experimentally verified and so one may ask: How can one now argue that an interaction does not occur at $dx \rightarrow 0, dt \rightarrow 0$? We note that experimentally, emitted and absorbed photons have tiny wavelengths. In a macroscopic world, these lengths would be considered essentially 0 and so for these numbers, there is no contradiction with Newton's results. A calculation of an electric bound to an atom, however, involves tiny lengths and so the $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ scenario would apply in such a situation, we argue.

Special Relativity

A photon and a massive particle seem to be physically very different, but they have the notion of p and E in common as well as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (according to the above section). Special relativity establishes the transformation of E and p . If one considers that a massive particle has a rest mass then one may link its E and p to m_0 and v and use $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$. If, however, one has E, pc for a massive particle and is only interested in the Lorentz transformation based on another moving frame, then one deals with E_1, p_1 and E_2, p_2 and the transformation is the same for both a photon and particle with rest mass. In other words, special relativity includes both photons and massive particles and transforms them in the same way. Now, for a photon, special relativity yields $E=pc$ and we have argued in previous notes that E and p being interaction variables should not yield an equation so close to $x=ct$ unless the interaction variables are also responsible for the photon's motion in some kind of force:action/reaction manner. If this is the case, then the stochasticity of photon hits is present in special relativity and if photons and massive particles can interact, (photon emission/absorption) then again, one would assume that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ holds for both a photon and massive particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our main point is that a photon seems to interact via E and p in a stochastic manner linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This math form is consistent with 2-slit interference and Maxwell's photon solution, but its interpretation as a probability for interaction is consistent with Einstein's 1905 photoelectric ideas. We suggest that if a photon may interact with a massive particle, e.g. an atom in a photon absorption or emission problem, then if the photon is described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for stochastic interactions, then the massive particle must also be described in an identical manner. We further suggest and show that this stochastic view must conserve momentum. Finally, we argue that special relativity is consistent with this viewpoint.